

INVESTIGATE IMPLEMENTATION OF GUIDANCE AND COUNSELLING SERVICES IN CHILDHOOD EDUCATION UNDER A RECESSED ECONOMY: A STUDY ON PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract

The study investigated implementation of guidance and counselling services in childhood education under a recessed economy: a study on primary schools in Anambra State. Two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant. the descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population of the study consist of all the ninety-five (95) guidance counsellors working in the primary schools of Anambra state. Both professional (teacher-counsellors). The sample consists of ninety -five (95) professional counsellors and Non-professional (Teacher-Counsellor) in primary schools in Anambra State. Copies of the questionnaire were distributed to each of the 95-Professional counsellors and Non-Professional (Teacher-counsellors) that constitute the sample. Considering the small size, the researcher distributed the questionnaire to school counsellors in selected primary schools. The copies of the questionnaire which were 95 in number are issued by hand directly to the counsellors. The hypotheses were tested by a computation of the t-distribution. The finding of the study revealed that professional counsellors and teacher-counsellors do not differ significantly in their mean rating on the attitudes of other school personnel (teachers and headmaster) hinder the effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in primary schools in Anambra state. Recommendation was made that, for sustainable development in education government should make educational policies that will not allow any socio-economic problems that arises in the society to easily influence the education system.

Introduction

In topical times, the problem of global economic recession and its negative impacts on the well-being of citizens of nations, Nigeria inclusive has been drawing the attention of

researchers scholars and policy makers. In Nigeria, this situation has posed a lot of challenges such as increased youths unemployment, violence attacks, stealing and kidnapping activities by youths to list but some (Amazue & Okoli, 2004). According to Dike (2009) about 80% of Nigerian youths are unemployed while about 10% of the employed are underemployed. Amazue and Okoli (2004) remarked that youths' unemployment tends to account for their involvement in social crimes and over dependence on government for employment. Implicitly, it could adduced that curbing these problems calls for proper guidance and counselling of school pupils and retooling of Nigeria educational policy to incorporate effective guidance's services in primary school education.

Lately in Nigeria generally and in the South Eastern States of Nigeria in particular effects of economic recession have made many parents unable to pay their children's' school fees. Parents, particularly civil servants and retirees from public sector of the economy have been so impoverished by months of unpaid salaries, pensions and other allowances accruing to them (ANON, 2016) that they have no other means of meeting up with their family needs. Many of these pupils are now being deprived of school, in most case parents now involve their children in some forms of trades such as, they hawk in the morning before going to school, some leave the school and go to hawk when they feel that no serious studies are going on in the school, another group go hawking after school while so many absent themselves from school completely and go hawking for a whole day. Continuous absenteeism from school emanating from economic-recession has affected pupil's attendance of school.

Moreover, parents who have regular means of livelihood like civil servants, renown traders, artisans, and craftsmen have hitherto still have challenges in financing their children education in this season of economy recession Nigeria is going through and the government

of the day have been unable to live up to its promise and expectation from the citizens. With economic recession in Nigeria some of these parents, particularly the civil servants, who are owed months of salaries (ANON, 2016) have no choice but to send their children/wards to the streets to hawk some goods to make money to help the family, especially in feeding, having closed their eyes to the negative effects. No doubt, Obunadike (2013) remarked that when pupils are properly guided and counselled, their over dependency on government for employment will reduce and they would become more of employers of labour than seekers of jobs which could aid any nation to come out of economy recession. Guidance and Counselling is one of the educational services.

However, educational services as contained in the National Policy of Education (2004) are to facilitate the implementation of the educational policy, the attainment of policy goals and the promotion of effectiveness of educational system. Again the third goal of the educational services is to “make learning experiences more meaningful for children. Based on these goals, the guidance and counselling activities in schools are beneficial because what the counsellors working with pupils in primary schools guide them thoroughly to help them succeed in their educational pursuit. According to Okobiah and Okorodudu (2006) Guidance and Counselling is encompassed by activities of relevant services and also processes of helping persons within and outside the school, to achieve their full potentialities in their emotional, moral, social, academic and vocational developments. In this paper, the focus is on the implementation of guidance and counselling services in childhood education under a recessed economy: a study on primary schools in Anambra State. Based on the need by government of the day to see that as much as possible that children are given compulsory

primary school education. It is as a result of this that the authors of this paper sought to find out whether the present economic recession has affected the implementation of counselling programmes in schools with or without counsellors in order to help make necessary recommendations for greater achievement in the educational sector of the state especially, with the free and compulsory education scheme in place.

There are conveying services which pupils gain from counselling sessions. These services include information, placement, guidance, referral, and follow-up (Akinade, 2002). In essence, counselling is a cognitive educational service which provides accurate, reliable and valid information about opportunities in the society. It is the duty of a trained guidance counsellor to perform these roles. Therefore, counselling encourages pupils to accept full responsibility and utilization of their potentials to maximize opportunities available in their environment. A Guidance Counsellor which can also be referred to as School Counsellor according to Ifelunni (1997) is a trained expert who is exposed to enough psychology necessary to understand and predict human behaviours.

Guidance Counsellors are primarily saddled with the responsibility of facilitating a total and holistic development of individuals who will be useful to themselves and the society. Specifically, their roles according to Denga (2001) involves Counselling, planning and developing of Guidance programmes, appraising, interpreting and making appropriate referrals to relevant specialists on problems and issues that fall outside their competence orbit. Other roles of guidance counsellors include researching, evaluating and organizing programmes, attending conference and workshops, disseminating information including career awareness creation. Guidance and counselling in primary schools is riddled with a number of problems which are attitudinal, structural, human and cultural. These include

malfunction to engage in careful analysis of organizational problems that guidance and counselling was intended to resolve. There have been lack of trained school counsellors in primary schools and colleges, and lack of sufficient time, facilities and orientation materials for use by counsellors. The experiences of guidance personnel in both Nigeria and elsewhere have revealed so many problem areas hindering the effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in schools as shown under cultural consideration developmental pattern, personnel for guidance and counselling services.

However, available literature has not revealed any specific study on the problems hindering the effective implementation of Guidance and counselling services in primary schools in Anambra State. The problems hindering an effective implementation of guidance and counseling are not expected to be different from what is obtainable in some of her sister State in the federation. Professional School counsellors who are directly involved in the implementation of guidance and counselling programme in some of the primary school in Anambra State are in position to experience the nature of the impediments to effective implementation of guidance and counselling services. It is against this background that actually motivated the researcher to carry-out

The study on the implementation of guidance and counselling services in childhood education under a recessed economy: a study on primary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Guidance counsellors are professional posted to schools to render the guidance and counselling services in some of the school. Most of the primary schools in the state have no guidance counsellors at all, while the few that can be found in a few schools have been assigned teaching subjects. The result of this negative attitude towards , guidance and

counselling is that most of the primary school pupils in some urban and 'rural areas have been deprived of the valuable services which the programme offers to pupils in educational institutions in Nigeria and elsewhere in the world.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate implementation of guidance and counselling services in childhood education under a recessed economy: a study on primary schools in Anambra State.

Hypotheses

In further pursuance of the purpose of this study the following hypotheses is tested.

1. The responses of professional counsellors and teacher-counsellors do not differ significantly in their mean rating on the attitudes of other school personnel (teachers and principals) hinder the effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in primary schools ($P < 0.05$).
2. The responses of professional counsellors and teacher-counsellors does not differ significantly in their mean rating on the extent does the availability of tools, equipment's and facilities impede on the effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in primary schools ($P < 0.05$).

Method

To carry out this study the descriptive survey research design was adopted. This is because the study described the in-situ situation of implementation of guidance and counselling

services in childhood education under a recessed economy: a study on primary schools in Anambra State. The population of the study was all the ninety-five (95) guidance counsellors working in the secondary schools of Anambra state. Both professional (teacher-counsellors).

The sample consists of ninety -five (95) professional counsellors and Non-professional (Teacher-Counsellor) in primary schools in Anambra State. Copies of the questionnaire were distributed to each of the 95-Professional counsellors and Non-Professional (Teacher-counsellors) that constitute the sample. Considering the small size, the researcher distributed the questionnaire to school counsellors in selected primary schools. The copies of the questionnaire which were 95 in number are issued by hand directly to the counsellors. The hypotheses were tested by a computation of the t-distribution.

Results

H₀₁The responses of professional counsellors and teacher-counsellors do not differ significantly in their mean rating on the attitudes of other school personnel (teachers and headmaster) hinder the effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in primary schools (P< 0.05).

Table 1: Test of differences between professional counsellors and teacher-counsellors do not differ significantly in their mean rating on the attitudes of other school personnel (teachers and headmaster) hinder the effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in primary schools

Respondents	N	x	SD	Df	t-cal	t-critical	Remark
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headmaster	33	14.30	1.72				
Teachers	62	13.96	2.68	93	1.02	2.00	NS
Total	95	14.13	2.24				

NS = Not significant t-crit. =

2.00

Result from the table above depicts that the calculated t-value observed was 1.02 as the different between of professional counsellors and teacher-counsellors do not differ significantly in their mean rating on the attitudes of other school personnel (teachers and headmaster) hinder the effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in primary schools. This calculated t-value is therefore not significant since it is lesser than the critical t- value of 2.00 given 93 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significant. This led to the upholding of the null hypothesis that professional counsellors and teacher-counsellors do not differ significantly in their mean rating on the attitudes of other school personnel (teachers and headmaster) hinder the effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in primary schools in primary schools in Anambra state.

H₀₂ The responses of professional counsellors and teacher-counsellors does not differ significantly in their mean rating on the extent does the availability of tools, equipment's and facilities impede on the effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in primary schools (P< 0.05).

Table 2: t-test for Difference in the responses of professional counsellors and teacher-counsellors does not differ significantly in their mean rating on the extent does the availability of tools, equipment's and facilities impede on the effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in primary schools

Respondents	N	x	SD	Df	t-cal	t-critical	Remark
professional	25	69.89	13.09				
teacher-	70	43.14	10.67	93	2.03	2.00	NS
Total	95						

NS = Not significant t-crit. = 2.00

From Table 2, the calculated t-test of 2.03 which is greater than the table value of 1.96 is significant at 0.05 levels. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis which holds that there is significant difference between professional counsellors and teacher-counsellors in their mean rating on the extent does the availability of tools, equipment's and facilities impede on the effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in primary schools it is upheld.

Discussion of Result

Based on this study the researcher observed that there is a decline in availability of tools, equipment's and facilities impede on the effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in primary schools Anambra States. This trend is an anomaly in a country where the fertility rate of adolescents is high and where the general population is on the increase. This according to Besong (2010) is not good for Nigeria's general development. Besong (2010) opined that this trend will impact negatively on students' access to formal education. This tallies with the results of the hypothesis test where both here is significant difference between professional counsellors and teacher-counsellors in their mean rating on the extent does the availability of tools, equipment's and facilities impede on the effective implementation of guidance and counselling services in primary schools in Anambra state.

Implications of the Study

An educational implication of this study is that economic recession is experienced in all the states studied and economic recession has similar influence on the implementation of guidance and counselling services in primary schools in Anambra state. The state will likely suffer the brunt of having more illiterate persons created during this economic recession when their economies recover. Further, the states will suffer in future fighting adult illiteracy rather than concentrating and directing their resources towards improved educational developments.

Conclusions

Economic recession has drastically affected educational development. Professional counsellors and Teachers-counsellors are owed months of salaries; and adequate materials need for the full implementation of counselling services in primary schools are not sufficient.

Recommendations

Based on this study the following recommendations were made: for sustainable development in education government should make educational policies that will not allow any socio-economic problems that arises in the society to easily influence the education system.

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